

Electrochemical reactions at sacrificial electrodes : Direct electrochemical synthesis of cadmium(II) alkoxides and their coordination compounds

Baljit Singh* and Kanchan Bala

Department of Chemistry, Punjabi University, Patiala-147 002, Punjab, India

E-mail : baljit_chemz@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 06 October 2009, revised 02 June 2010, accepted 14 June 2010

Abstract : Electrochemical reactions of hexan-1-ol, heptan-1-ol, octan-1-ol, nonan-1-ol, decan-1-ol at sacrificial cadmium anode and inert platinum cathode yield cadmium(II) alkoxides, $\text{Cd}(\text{OR})_2$, using acetonitrile as solvent and tetrabutylammonium chloride as supporting electrolyte. On refluxing with 2,2'-bipyridyl (L) these alkoxides do not form coordination compounds. However, compounds with general formula $\text{Cd}(\text{OR})_2 \cdot \text{L}$ have been isolated by electrolysis of the solutions of above alcohols in the presence of ligand (L) at cadmium anode. The products have been characterised by elemental analysis and infrared spectral studies. Current efficiencies of all these reactions are quite high.

Keywords : Electrochemical reactions, sacrificial electrode, cadmium(II) alkoxides.

Introduction

Electrochemical technique represents a green route in synthetic inorganic and organic chemistry^{1,2} and the most important advantage of this technique is simplicity and high product yield³ and several other advantages⁴. Cadmium(II) alkoxides are valuable precursors for extra-pure metal oxides and the synthesis of nano particles⁵ which is a burning topic now-a-days. A survey of literature^{6,7} reveals that no systematic attempt has been made to synthesise and study cadmium(II) alkoxides of higher alcohols⁸ and their coordination compounds. In continuation of our interest in electrochemical synthesis of inorganic compounds^{9,10}, synthesis of cadmium(II) alkoxides and their coordination compounds with 2,2'-bipyridyl has been reported in this communication. In electrochemical reactions of alcohols at sacrificial metal anode, metal alkoxides is formed as a result of replacement of proton of alcohol molecules with anodic metal.

Experimental

Reagents and solvent : Acetonitrile was dried over phosphorous pentoxide, double distilled and was used as solvent. Tetrabutylammonium chloride was crystallised from conductivity water, dried under reduced pressure at 100 °C and was used as supporting electrolyte in these systems, hexan-1-ol, heptan-1-ol, octan-1-ol, nonan-1-ol and decan-1-ol were used as supplied.

Procedure and technique : Electrolysis was carried out in H-type cell made of pyrex glass having anode and cathode compartments separated from each other by a sintered glass disc of G-4 porosity. Platinum foil ($1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$) and cadmium rod ($2 \times 10 \times 0.2 \text{ cm}^3$) were used as cathode and sacrificial anode respectively. Both the outlets of H-type cell were fitted with guard tubes and were sealed in order to protect the products from direct contact with air or moisture. Solution of tetrabutylammonium chloride (1.0 g) and 5 ml of alcohol in 250 ml of acetonitrile was taken in electrochemical cell. Necessary connections were made with the power supply and potential across the electrodes was so adjusted that a current of about 20 mA passed through the cell. The electrolytic cell can be represented as :

$\text{Cd}_{(+)}$ is cadmium sacrificial anode and

$\text{Pt}_{(-)}$ is platinum cathode.

Electrolysis was carried out for about ten hours with continuous stirring. As the electrolysis proceeded, white coloured solid product started separating in the anode compartment. These products were filtered, washed repeatedly with warm acetonitrile and dry ether in the glass filtration unit, and dried in vacuum. The coordination compounds of these products of alcohols were prepared

in similar way except that 1.0 g of ligand 2,2'-bipyridyl was also added in addition to other substrates before starting electrolysis. The current efficiencies (gram equivalents of metal dissolved per Faraday) of all these reactions were determined by electrolyzing the above systems for exactly two hours at a constant current of 20 mA. The ratio of experimental cadmium contents to theoretical cadmium contents gives the current efficiency^{10b}.

Results and discussion

Electrochemical reactions of alcohols at sacrificial cadmium anode and inert platinum cathode yield cadmium(II) alkoxides. The mechanism of the reaction is given below :

At inert cathode :

At sacrificial anode :

The mechanism of coordination compounds of alcohols at sacrificial cadmium anode and inert platinum cathode with ligand 2,2'-bipyridyl is given below :

At inert cathode :

At sacrificial anode :

Cadmium contents in all these products were determined by oxine¹¹ method. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen (where applicable) contents in these products were determined by using CHN analyser. Cadmium and alcohol correspond to 1 : 2 stoichiometry respectively and conforms to $\text{Cd}(\text{OR})_2$ in case of alkoxides and $\text{Cd}(\text{OR})_2 \cdot \text{L}$ in case of their adducts with the ligand 2,2'-bipyridyl. The products of these electrochemical reactions are not affected much by moisture or air and are quite stable. Melting point of all these products was determined using electrical device with a heating rate of 5 °C per minute. It has been observed that these compounds do not melt upto 300 °C but decompose at a temperature around 220 °C. The decomposition of products is indicated from the change in colour of these compounds. All these compounds are insoluble in all the commonly used organic solvents like methanol, ethanol, chloroform, acetone, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, *N,N*-dimethyl formamide, dimethyl sulfoxide and toluene.

Infrared spectra of the products have been recorded using Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer (RXI) in the region of 4000–450 cm^{-1} using potassium bromide pallets. It has been observed that all of these compounds do not show any absorption band in the region of 3600–3400 cm^{-1} corresponding to hydroxyl group¹² of alcohols which show that the product is completely free from alcohol and solvated alkoxides. However, characteristic bands appear in the region of 1150–1000 cm^{-1} and 550–450 cm^{-1} . Survey of literature reveals¹³ that the Metal-Oxygen stretching frequency in metal alkoxides appear in the region of 600–400 cm^{-1} . Thus the absorption bands present in the region of 550–450 cm^{-1} in the present studies may be assigned to $\nu(\text{Cd-O})$ stretching¹³ vibrations. Presence of these bands and absence of band due to hydroxyl group in the electrochemical products indicate that the hydrogen of the alcohols have been replaced by the anodic cadmium. Review of literature reveals^{9,14} that the absorption bands due to $\nu(\text{C-O})\text{M}$ stretching vibrations appear in the region of 1170–950 cm^{-1} in various metal alkoxides. Transition metal alkoxides generally exist as polymers by forming bridged structure through alkoxy groups. It has been reported^{9,10,14} that infrared data of metal alkoxides show the existence of two types of $\nu(\text{C-O})\text{M}$ absorption bands. The terminal alkoxide groups show absorption bands in the region of 1170–1040 cm^{-1} and bridged alkoxides groups show absorption in the region of 1040–950 cm^{-1} . Infrared spectra of the present electrochemical products show the appearance of two/three absorption bands in the region of 1150–1000 cm^{-1} . Infrared spectra of these compounds also reveal that bands appeared due to bridged alkoxide groups in case of compounds of hexan-1-ol, heptan-1-ol, octan-1-ol are of medium intensity whereas bands due to terminal alkoxide groups are weak. But in case of compounds of nonan-1-ol and decan-1-ol, the bands due to bridged alkoxide groups are weak. This is due to the fact that as number of carbon atoms increases, degree of polymerisation decreases thereby the intensity of bridged alkoxide groups decreases.

Cadmium(II) alkoxides were refluxed with 2,2'-bipyridyl in various solvents like methanol, ethanol, acetonitrile, benzene etc. for more than 48 h. However, the coordination compounds could not be prepared which was evident from the analytical and IR data. The coordination compounds, however, could be prepared easily by elec-

trochemical processes as discussed above. Infrared spectra of these coordination compounds show $\nu(\text{C-O})_{\text{Cd}}$ and $\nu(\text{Cd-O})$ modes like their parent alkoxides in the respective regions^{9,14} with the only difference that these bands appear slightly in the higher region (+10 to 20 cm^{-1}). Moreover $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{C})$ and $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ modes due to ligand molecules are also present in the adducts around 1600 cm^{-1} which otherwise are absent in the parent alkoxides thereby confirming that the ligand molecule has been added.

Current efficiencies of all these systems have also been determined and are quite high (in the range of 0.75 to 0.85 gram equivalents/Faraday) thereby showing that the reactions leading to the formation of cadmium(II) alkoxides and their co-ordination compounds are the predominant reactions of these systems.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors Kanchan Bala is thankful to Punjab State Council for Science and Technology for the financial help.

References

1. Micheal A. Methews, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 2001, **73**, 1305.
2. E. Steckhan, T. Ams, W. R. Heineman, G. Hitt, D. Hoorman, J. Joriseen, L. Krone, B. Lewall and H. Putter, *Chemosphere*, 2001, **43**, 63.
3. J. S. Banait, S. K. Deol and Baljit Singh, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1990, **20**, 1331.
4. D. G. Tuck, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 2005, **51**, 1979.
5. Timothy J. Boyle, Scott D. Bunge, Todd M. Alam, Gregory P. Holland, Thomas J. Headley and Gabriel Avilucea, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2005, **44**, 1309.
6. A. J. Bloodworth and J. Serlin, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans 1*, 1973, 261.
7. D. C. Bradley, R. C. Mehrotra and D. P. Gaur, "Metal Alkoxides", Academic Press, New York, 1978.
8. J. S. Banait and Baljit Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 895.
9. Baljit Singh and Harpreet Kaur, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **85**, 849.
10. (a) J. S. Banait, Baljit Singh and Sarbjit Rala, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **86**, 416; (b) J. S. Banait, Bhagirath Lal and Baljit Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **71**, 543.
11. Vogel's, "Text Book of Quantitative Chemical Analysis", Longman Group UK, Ltd., 1989, 397.
12. M. Avram and Gh. Matiescu, "Infrared Spectroscopy Applications in Organic Chemistry", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1972.
13. R. W. Adams, C. G. Barraclough, R. L. Martin and G. Winter, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1967, **20**, 2351.
14. D. C. Bradely, R. C. Mehrotra, I. P. Rothwell and A. Singh, "Alkoxo and Aryloxo Derivatives of Metals", Academic Press, New York, 2001.
15. J. R. Dyer, "Application of Absorption Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds", Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, 1978.

